

Amine Exchange Reactions of Tertiary-N-Mannich Bases with Primary Aromatic Amines

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Manuscript received 28 November 1974; revised 7 March 1975; accepted 29 April 1975

THE exchange reactions¹⁻³ between β -amino ketones (tertiary-N-Mannich bases) and primary aromatic amines yield β -arylamino ketones e.g., I.

Similar exchange reactions with N-Mannich bases have not been reported so far. In this communication the exchange reactions of N-Mannich bases

aromatic amines such as aniline, *m*-toluidine, *m*-chloroaniline, methyl-4-amino-benzoate, ethyl-4-aminobenzoate and 4-aminodiphenyl. The exchanged products thus obtained are summarised in Table I.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are not corrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr discs. NMR spectrum was obtained on a Varian A-60 Spectrometer in CDCl_3 using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard.

3-Dimethylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2 (V)⁵, 3-dimethylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2-thione (VI)⁶, 3-piperidinomethyl-6-nitrobenzoxazolinone-2 (VII)⁷, and N-(dimethylaminomethyl)-phthalimide (VIII)⁸ were prepared according to the published procedures.

Amine Exchange Reactions (Table 1):

Mixture of a tertiary-N-Mannich base (0.01 mole), aromatic amine (0.01 mole) and ethanol (15 ml)

with primary aromatic amines are being reported for the first time. Tertiary-N-Mannich bases(II) furnish corresponding arylaminomethyl analogs(IV) in good yields⁴ when treated with aromatic amines (equation 1). The exchanged products(IV) were adequately characterised with the help of i.r, n.m.r. and elemental analysis.

The tertiary-N-Mannich bases (V, VI, VII and VIII) were subjected to exchange reactions with

was refluxed on a steam bath for 1 hr. The reaction was allowed to cool to room temp. The solid product thus obtained was filtered and washed with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60^o-80^o) and recrystallised from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Head of the Chemistry Department for providing laboratory facilities and to Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow; and

TABLE I

S.No.	Tertiary-N-Mannich base	Aromatic amine	Exchanged product	M.P. °C	M. P. °C	M.P. °C		I.R. (μ) NH
						Mixed with authentic sample	C = O (Ring)	
1.	V	Aniline	IX ^a	171-172	174-175 (9)	169-170	5.70	2.92
2.	V	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	X	157-158	156-157 (9)	—	5.65	2.95
3.	V	Methyl-4-aminobenzoate	XI ^a	210-211	210-212 (10)	210-211	5.67	2.92
4.	VII	Aniline	XII ^d	168	—	168	5.65	2.90
5.	VII	4-Aminodiphenyl	XIII ^a	186-188	188-190 (11)	190-192	5.65	2.90
6.	VI	Aniline	XIV ^{a,f}	164-167	167-169 (12)	164-167	—	3.00
7.	VIII	Aniline	XV	146	145.5 (13)	—	5.60 5.80	2.92
8.	VIII	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	XVI	135-136	138-139 (13)	—	—	—
9.	VIII	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	XVII	166-167	169 (13)	—	—	—
10.	VIII	Ethyl-4-aminobenzoate	XVIII	173-174	176.5 (13)	—	—	—

^a, Its i.r. was identical with the i.r. of the authentic sample. ^b, 5.80 (C = O ester). ^c, 6.50 and 7.40 (NO₂).
^d, Anal.: Calc. for C₁₄H₁₁N₃O₄: C, 58.95; H, 3.88; N, 14.73. Found: C, 58.87; H, 4.19; N, 14.69.
^e, 6.45 and 7.40 (NO₂). ^f, NMR: δ 5.65 (singlet-CH₂- β); 6.7-7.50 (aromatic 9H and NH).

Smith Kline and French Laboratories, Philadelphia, Pa. U.S.A. for spectral and elemental data.

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Possible Anti-Parkinsonian Compounds. Part-IX.

Synthesis of 1,3,4-Substituted Catechol Derivatives

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Manuscript received 17 January 1975; accepted 19 May 1975,

SOME now 1,3,4-substituted catechol derivatives have been synthesised with a view to testing their anti-parkinsonian activity.

It has been confirmed by the biochemical, histochemical and neuropharmacological studies that catecholamines play a very vital role in the central control of motor functions. The researches of Carlsson¹ and Hornykiewicz² have further confirmed these findings. These authors demonstrated the loss of dopamine β -(3 : 4-dihydroxy-phenylethylamine) in the corpus-striatum and substantia-nigra of the brain. The level of other biogenic amines viz., norepinephrine and serotonin was also found to be lowered but not to the extent that dopamine is lowered. In addition succinic and malonic acid-derivatives have also been found to possess considerable anti-parkinsonism effect³. Based on these observations the authors thought it desirable to extend the work on catechol moiety with the expectations that these compounds might render better therapeutic results.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

N-Hydroxyethyl-phthalimide/succinimide :

The method described by Vogel⁴ was followed.

I. 1-Methyl-benzamido/phthalimido/nicotinamido/o-acetylsalicylamido-catechol (I) :

A mixture of catechol (0.01 mole), formalin (0.012 mole) and benzamide/phthalimide/nicotinamide/o-acetyl-salicylamide and few drops of conc. HCl was dissolved in 30 ml. methanol by warming. Subsequently the reaction mixture was stirred for 1 hr at room temperature and then refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. After removing methanol by distillation, a crude product was obtained, which